

Main welfare aspects of stunning broilers by exposure to controlled atmosphere

Introduction

- There are two main types of stunning systems commercially used in poultry, electrical waterbath stunning (**WBS**) and controlled atmosphere stunning (**CAS**).
- CAS consists in exposing the chickens to modified gas environments or by reducing the atmosphere pressure, which induce a gradual loss of consciousness.
- WBS is used in both small-scale and large-scale abattoirs, while CAS is nearly always used in large-scale abattoirs, likely because CAS systems involve large investments but also increase the slaughter capacity.

Proportion of slaughterhouses (left) and slaughtered chickens (right) according to the different stunning methods used in the European Union in 2021. Data extracted from 20 out of 27 European Member States that replied a EURCAW-Poultry-SFA survey.

CAS methods

- Stunning with carbon dioxide (CO₂) in two phases
- Stunning with inert gases
- Stunning with carbon dioxide associated with inert gases
- Low atmospheric pressure stunning (LAPS)

Available equipment

Currently, CO₂ in two phases is by far the most common CAS method in use in the European Union.

- Tunnel
- Closed cabinet
- Pit

Percentage of the different CO₂ stunning equipment that are currently in use in European Union. Data extracted from 20 out of 27 European Member States that replied a EURCAW-Poultry-SFA survey in 2021.

Advantages of CAS

- No uncrating and shackling conscious birds.
- Stunning can be either reversible or irreversible.
- When irreversible, it prevent from recovery before death occurs.

CAS welfare concerns

- Induction of unconsciousness is not instantaneous and involves a transitional period during which negative welfare outcomes may occur.
- CAS systems may incorporate windows or cameras for monitoring the behaviour of the animals. However, it does not allow a clear view of all animals.

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1. Stunning with CO₂ in two phases

 Broilers are first exposed to low concentration of CO₂ (up to 40%) until unconsciousness occurs. Thereafter, the CO₂ concentration is increased in the second phase inducing a deeper state of unconsciousness and then death.

- • It renders the bird unconscious when using a low level of CO₂ (< 40%) followed by a second phase where broilers are killed painlessly with exposure to a high CO₂ concentrations.
- • If birds are conscious, concentrations of CO₂ at above 40% cause unpleasant sensation, pain and respiratory distress when inhaled. This could occur when the exposure time in the first phase is too short leading to animals arriving conscious in the second phase in which CO₂ is above 40%.

3. Stunning with CO₂ associated with inert gases

 Broilers are induced to unconsciousness by direct or progressive exposure to a gas mixture containing CO₂ up to 40% associated and inert gases.

- • Broilers tolerate the inhalation of concentrations below 40% CO₂, inert gases are imperceptible to birds and the reduction of available oxygen is not perceived either.
- The duration of induction to unconsciousness is shorter than with inert gases
- The occurrence of vigorous convulsions expressed as wing flapping in unconscious birds are less pronounced than the other CAS methods and thus, the likelihood of unconscious animal while convulsing to harm neighbouring birds that are still conscious is lowered.

2. Stunning with inert gases

 Broilers are exposed to inert gas mixtures with a maximum of 2% residual oxygen, leading to loss of consciousness. Inert gases displace oxygen from the atmospheric air and this ensures that the birds are stunned by anoxia (i.e., lack of oxygen) and dead if the duration of the process is prolonged enough.

- • Inhalation of inert gases do not cause aversive reactions after initial exposure, as they are imperceptible to birds.
- • After loss of consciousness, birds can perform severe convulsion which may produce wing fractures as well as injuries and distress to other birds that have not yet lost consciousness.
- The duration of induction to unconsciousness is longer than with CO₂ in two phases. If birds are not exposed enough time, they can recover consciousness rapidly if breathing atmospheric air at the exit of the stunning system

4. LAPS

 Broilers are induced to a non-recovery state of unconsciousness through progressive hypobaric anoxia (i.e., lack of oxygen due to lowered atmospheric pressure)

- • It produces a non-recovery state of birds and thus, it does not compromise the welfare of the bird during the following slaughtering procedures.
- • Pain may happen since defecation and prolapses of cloaca were observed during LAPS suggesting expansion of gas trapped in gut and probably also in other body cavities.
- • **Only approved for the stunning of broilers of less than 4 kg** of body weight according to a prescribed pressure curve carefully described in the implementing regulation.

Related to controlled atmosphere stunning methods

<p>Carbon dioxide in two phases, inert gases or in carbon dioxide in association with inert gases: Specific requirements</p>	<p>COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 1099/2009 {Annex I; Chapter II}</p> <p> “8. Under no circumstances shall gases enter into the chamber or the location where animals are to be stunned and killed in a way that it could create burns or excitement by freezing or lack of humidity”</p>
<p>Carbon dioxide in two phases, inert gases or in carbon dioxide in association with inert gases: Gas stunning equipment</p>	<p>COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) No 1099/2009 {Annex II}</p> <p> “6.2. Gas stunners shall be equipped to measure continuously, display and record the gas concentration and the time of exposure, and to give a clearly visible and audible warning if the concentration of gas falls below the required level. The device shall be placed so as to be clearly visible to the personnel. These records shall be kept for at least one year. Gas stunners shall be designed in a manner that, even at the maximum permitted throughput, the animals are able to lie down without being stacked on each other.”</p>
<p>LAPS: General requirements</p>	<p>COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) 2018/723 of 16 May 2018 amending Annexes I and II to Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009 {Annex I, Chapter 2, point 10}</p> <p> “10.5 Records of absolute vacuum pressure, time of exposure, temperature and humidity shall be kept for at least one year.”</p>
<p>LAPS: Layout, construction and equipment of slaughterhouses</p>	<p>COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) 2018/723 of 16 May 2018 amending Annexes I and II to Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009 {Annex II; point 7}</p> <p> “7.2. The system shall be equipped to measure continuously, display and record the absolute vacuum pressure, the time of exposure, the temperature, the humidity and to give a clearly visible and audible warning if the pressure deviates from the required levels. The device shall be clearly visible to the personnel.”</p>